

Chemical investigation of the roots of *Xanthium strumarium*

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Abstract : Chemical investigation of the methanolic extract of the roots of *Xanthium strumarium* (compositae) has resulted in the isolation of stigmasterol-3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (1), 2-methylanthraquinone (2) and stigmasterol. Although stigmasterol was reported earlier from the aerial part of his plant, but there was no report of isolation of 1 and 2 from this plant source. This is the first report of isolation of 1 and 2 from this plant with detailed spectral and chemical studies.

Compound 1 though reported earlier to be present in minute quantity in a fraction containing a mixture of sterols but there was no report of its detailed spectral and chemical studies. Compound 2, even though a known compound, has not been isolated from this plant before.

Keyword : *Xanthium strumarium*, stigmasterol-3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside, 2-methylanthraquinone.

Xanthium strumarium (compositae), commonly known as *Bonokra*, is a medium sized herb widely grows in the plains of West Bengal and neighbouring states in India and is well known for its medicinal value. In the Indian system of medicine, the whole plant is used as diaphoretic, sedative, sudorific and in the treatment of long standing malaria while the root of this plant is used as bitter tonic and also in the treatment of cancer and strumous diseases¹. The plant has also been reported to possess hypoglycemic², anti-diabetic³, modulators of human mesangial cell proliferation⁴, anti-trypanosomal⁵, cytotoxic⁶, anti-fungal⁷ and a variety of other biological activities^{8,9}.

Earlier investigations on the plant, particularly on the aerial parts, reported the isolation of several compounds such as xanthanol, isoxanthanol, carboxyatractyloside, xanthiazone, caffeic acid, 1,5-di-*O*-caffeoylquinic acid, 1,3,5-tri-*O*-caffeoylquinic acid and some other compounds like xantholides, xanthane epoxide, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, and poriferasterol¹⁰⁻¹⁷. Although the chemistry of the aerial parts of the plant has been studied over the years, little research has been done with the root^{17,18}. Therefore, the chemical investigation of the root of this plant has been adopted.

Results and discussion

The methanolic extract of the root of *Xanthium strumarium* was fractionated into two parts by extracting

with ethyl acetate (Fraction-I) and then with *n*-butanol (Fraction-II).

Chromatography (silica gel) of Fraction-II yielded a white crystalline compound (1), m.p. 289 °C while the Fraction-I yielded an orange-yellow crystalline solid (2), m.p.178 °C and a white crystalline compound (3), m.p. 163 °C.

Structure of compound 1 :

The IR spectrum of the compound 1 exhibited strong bands at 3345 and 1076 cm⁻¹ characteristic of a glycoside.

(1)

(2)

The FAB-mass spectrum showed the presence of a quasimolecular ion at m/z 597 $[M + Na]^+$ which suggested the molecular weight of the compound to be 574 corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{35}H_{58}O_6$. A characteristic peak at m/z 396 suggested the loss of a hexose fragment from the molecular ion.

The 1H NMR spectrum of the compound showed the signals at δ 0.67 and 0.96 due to the two tertiary methyls at Me-18 and Me-19 and four signals at δ 0.85, 0.83, 0.82 and 0.81 were due to four secondary methyls at Me-21, Me-26, Me-27 and Me-29, respectively. The signal at δ 5.34 corresponded to the tri-substituted olefinic proton H-6 and the signals at δ 5.15 and 5.12 were due to the two di-substituted olefinic protons H-22 and H-23, respectively.

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum showed the existence of 35 carbon atoms in the molecule. An anomeric signal at δ 100.8 indicated a monosaccharide moiety in the molecule. The degree of protonation of each carbon atom was determined by DEPT experiments. The ^{13}C (DEPT) NMR spectrum indicated the presence of six methyl, ten methylene and sixteen methine carbon atoms. The four methine signals at δ 70.0, 76.9, 73.4, 76.6 and one methylene signal at δ 61.0 were assigned for C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' carbon atoms, respectively of the β -D-glucopyranoside ring. The olefinic resonances at δ 121.0, 137.9 and 128.8 corresponded to the C-6, C-22 and C-23 methine carbon atoms while the resonance at δ 140.4 denoted the C-5 carbon atom of the sterol moiety.

Acetylation of the compound **1** with acetic anhydride and pyridine afforded the tetra-acetate derivative (**1A**). The positive FAB-mass spectrum of **1A** showed peaks at m/z 765 $[M + Na]^+$ and m/z 743 $[M+H]^+$ revealing the molecular weight to be 742 corresponding to molecular formula $C_{43}H_{66}O_{10}$. Acetylation deshielded all the methine protons alpha to acetates in the region δ 5.0–3.5. The signal for C-5'-H sugar proton at δ 3.69 was in considerably upfield position than in methyl- α -D-glucose tetraacetate. The sugar linkage in the above glucoside was thus assigned the β -configuration since the C-5'-H signal in β -glucoside was known¹⁹ to be shifted upfield from that of the α -anomer and its position remained unaffected²⁰ by the nature of the aglycone.

Acid hydrolysis of **1** yielded D-glucose and an aglycone (**1B**), which as identified as stigmaterol from its spectral data and also by direct comparison with an authentic sample (co-TLC, mmp).

Therefore, on the basis of all these findings compound **1** was identified as stigmaterol-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside.

Structure of **2** :

Elution of the column with petroleum ether-chloroform (1 : 3) gave a solid that was crystallised from petroleum ether-chloroform mixture as orange-yellow needles **2**, $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$, m.p. 178 °C.

IR spectrum of **2** exhibited strong bands at 1675 ($>C=O$) and 1593 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring). Mass spectrum of the compound showed molecular ion peak at m/z 222 (62%), and other peaks at m/z 207 $[M-CH_3]^+$ (6%), 194 $[M-CO]^+$ (31%), 165 $[M-2CO-H]^+$ (100%) characteristic of methylanthraquinone. The 1H NMR spectrum showed the presence of seven aromatic protons at δ 7.62 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz), 7.72–7.92 (2H, m), 8.12 (1H, br s), 8.24 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz), 8.3–8.4 (2H, m) and one aromatic methyl at δ 2.54 (3H, s). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the compound exhibited signals at δ 182.8 and 182.4 which were due to two carbonyl groups. The four close signals for quaternary carbon atoms appearing at δ 133.0, 133.2, 133.5 and 133.6 indicated the presence of an anthraquinone moiety. The presence of a broad signal at δ 8.12 (1H) as well as a signal at δ 21.6 for aromatic methyl in its ^{13}C NMR spectrum indicated that the methyl group was attached at C-2.

Therefore, based on all these findings the structure of the compound **2** was identified as 2-methylanthraquinone, which was further confirmed by its synthesis from phthalic anhydride.

Structure of **3** :

Fraction-I on chromatography over silica gel yielded a white crystalline compound **3**, $C_{29}H_{48}O$ (M^+ 412), m.p. 163 °C, identified as stigmaterol from its spectral data as well as by direct comparison with an authentic sample (co-TLC and mmp with an authentic compound).

Experimental

Except otherwise stated, all melting points were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and were uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded in JASCO FT-IR 410 spectrometers.

The mass spectra were recorded in JEOL JMS-600 mass-spectrometer and glycerol was used as the matrix for FAB-MS measurement. 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a BRUKER DPX-300 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard.

Extraction and fractionation :

Xanthium strumarium root (3 kg), collected locally, was exhaustively extracted with methanol at room temperature. The extract (2 lit.) was concentrated in a Ro-

tary Evaporator and extracted successively with ethyl acetate (Fraction-I, 5 g) and *n*-butanol (Fraction-II, 3 g).

Isolation of 1 : Fraction-II (3 g) was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel and the column was eluted with chloroform and chloroform-methanol mixtures. Elution with chloroform-methanol mixture (92 : 8) afforded compound **1** as white crystalline solid which was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixtures, m.p. 289 °C, (M^+ 574), R_f : 0.5 in $CHCl_3$ + MeOH (85 : 15); IR (KBr) 3345, 2918, 2850, 1639, 1538, 1470 cm^{-1} ; MS (FAB) m/z 597 (35%) [$M + Na$] $^+$, 396 (25%), 329 (100%); 1H NMR (δ ppm) 2.50 (2H, m), 1.23 (2H, m), 3.45 (1H, m), 1.50 (2H, m), 5.34 (1H, m), 1.16 (2H, m), 1.45 (1H, m), 0.87 (1H, dd), 2.49 (2H, m), 2.4 (2H, m), 1.0 (1H, m), 0.98 (2H, m), 2.4 (2H, br s), 0.96 (1H, m), 0.67 (3H, s), 0.96 (3H, s), 0.84 (1H, m), 0.85 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 5.15 (1H, m), 5.12 (1H, m), 0.80 (1H, m), 0.77 (1H, m), 0.83 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 0.82 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 0.78 (2H, m), 0.81 (3H, d, J 7.4 Hz), 4.2 (1H, d, J 5.8, Hz), 3.02 (1H, m), 3.11 (1H, m), 3.08 (1H, m), 3.06 (1H, m), 4.41 (2H, d, J 5.1 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) (δ ppm) 39.2 (C-1), 36.2 (C-2), 56.2 (C-3), 38.2 (C-4), 140.4 (C-5), 121.0 (C-6), 29.2 (C-7), 31.3 (C-8), 41.7 (C-9), 36.2 (C-10), 22.6 (C-11), 39.5 (C-12), 40.0 (C-13), 55.3 (C-14), 24.8 (C-15), 28.7 (C-16), 50.5 (C-17), 12.0 (C-18), 19.0 (C-19), 36.7 (C-20), 18.7 (C-21), 137.9 (C-22), 128.8 (C-23), 49.0 (C-24), 28.4 (C-25), 20.8 (C-26), 20.5 (C-27), 23.8 (C-28), 11.7 (C-29), 100.8 (C-1'), 70.0 (C-2'), 76.9 (C-3'), 73.4 (C-4'), 76.6 (C-5'), 61.0 (C-6').

Acetylation of 1 : 20 mg of **1** was dissolved in 0.1 ml of pyridine and 0.2 ml of acetic anhydride was added to it. The whole mass was kept at room temperature overnight. Then the reaction mixture was concentrated and poured into ice-cold water and shaken well to decompose excess of acetic anhydride. It was then extracted with chloroform (5 ml \times 4). The chloroform layer was washed with dil. HCl and water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Chloroform was removed to get the acetylated product (**1A**) (26 mg), m.p. 158 °C, (M^+ 742); IR (KBr) 2988, 1758, 1639, 1462 cm^{-1} ; MS m/z 765 (12%) [$M + Na$] $^+$, 743 (10%) [$M + H$] $^+$, 396 (25%), 55 (100%); 1H NMR (δ ppm) 1.03 (2H, m), 1.12 (2H, m), 3.68 (1H, br s), 1.47 (2H, m), 5.35 (1H, br s), 1.18 (2H, m), 1.15 (1H, m), 1.2 (1H, m), 2.22 (2H, m), 2.04 (2H, m), 1.2 (1H, m), 0.98 (2H, m), 2.07 (2H, m), 0.92 (1H, m), 0.67 (3H, s), 0.85 (3H, s), 0.82 (1H, m), 0.82 (3H, d, J 6.0 Hz), 5.2 (1H, m), 5.15 (1H, m), 0.80 (1H, m), 0.69 (1H, m), 0.86 (3H, d, J 6.0 Hz), 0.83 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz), 0.78 (2H, m), 0.89 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 4.6 (1H, d, J

5.6 Hz), 3.66 (1H, m), 4.1 (1H, m), 4.0 (1H, m), 3.69 (1H, m), 4.24 (2H, d, J 5.4 Hz), 2.02 (3H, s), 2.04 (3H, s), 2.07 (3H, s), 2.22 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (δ ppm) 39.0 (C-1), 36.7 (C-2), 56.0 (C-3), 39.7 (C-4), 140.4 (C-5), 122.1 (C-6), 29.7 (C-7), 31.8 (C-8), 51.2 (C-9), 36.7 (C-10), 21.1 (C-11), 38.9 (C-12), 39.7 (C-13), 56.0 (C-14), 29.7 (C-15), 31.9 (C-16), 56.9 (C-17), 12.2 (C-18), 19.3 (C-19), 36.8 (C-20), 21.0 (C-21), 138.3 (C-22), 129.4 (C-23), 29.5 (C-24), 29.2 (C-25), 20.8 (C-26), 24.3 (C-27), 25.4 (C-28), 12.0 (C-29), 99.7 (C-1'), 68.6 (C-2'), 73.0 (C-3'), 71.6 (C-4'), 71.8 (C-5'), 62.2 (C-6'), 170.7 and 19.4, 170.3 and 19.0, 169.4 and 20.7 and 169.3 and 20.6 (acetates $COCH_3$).

Acid hydrolysis of 1 : 20 mg of **1** was refluxed for 5 h over a steam-bath in 80% ethanolic 2(*N*) HCl solution. The reaction mixture was cooled, alcohol removed under vacuum, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether phase was washed with dilute Na_2CO_3 solution and then with water. The solvent was evaporated to get an aglycone (**1B**) (12 mg), crystallised from pet. ether-chloroform as colourless needles, m.p. 165 °C, $C_{29}H_{48}O$, M^+ 412. The compound **1B** was identified as stigmasterol by the comparison of spectral data with literature, and direct comparison of co-TLC and mmp with the authentic compound.

The aqueous part was neutralised by Ag_2CO_3 and filtered. The concentrated filtrate was found to contain D-glucose by TLC comparison with an authentic compound in the solvent system *n*-butanol-pyridine-water = (5 : 3 : 2).

Isolation of 2 and 3 : Fraction-I (5 g) was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel and eluted at first with petroleum ether and then subsequently with petroleum ether-chloroform mixtures and chloroform. Elution with pet. ether-chloroform mixture (1 : 1) afforded compound **3** as colourless crystalline solid, crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixtures, m.p. 163 °C whereas elution with petroleum ether-chloroform mixture (1 : 3) produced **2**, crystallised from ethanol as orange-yellow crystals, m.p. 178 °C, (M^+ 222); IR (KBr) 3320, 3020, 2920, 1675, 1593 1460 cm^{-1} ; MS m/z 222 (62%) [M^+], 207 (6%) [$M-CH_3$] $^+$, 194 (31%) [$M-CO$] $^+$, 165 (100%) [$M-2CO-H$] $^+$; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 2.54 (3H, s), 7.62 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz), 7.72–7.92 (2H, m), 8.12 (1H, br s), 8.24 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz), 8.3–8.4 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 127.1 (C-1), 144.9 (C-2), 130.9 (C-3), 127.0 (C-4), 133.2 (C-4a), 126.8 (C-5), 134.4 (C-6), 134.5 (C-7), 126.7 (C-8), 133.5 (C-8a), 182.8 (C-9), 133.0 (C-9a), 182.4 (C-10), 133.6 (C-10a), 21.6 (CH_3).

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